

HPC for ABM using Netlogo

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Abstract— the modeling of large-scale stochastic systems of heterogeneous individuals and their interactions, where multiple behaviors exist, requires a large number of scenarios and repetitions of simulation experiments. In these areas, the agent-based simulation (ABM) is the common tool and the High-Performance Computing can provide an adequate infrastructure for this type of simulations. The present work shows the methodology and the tools developed to allow the execution of multiple simulation scenarios based on ABM Netlogo model simulation in an HPC environment. The goal is to provide a user-friendly environment for ABM simulation to non-technological users.

Keywords-ABM, Simulation, Netlog, HPC.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the common problems with using High Performance Computing (HPC) environments for non-technological users, such as economists, biologists, epidemiologists, etc., is the complexity and difficulties involved with the configuration of the agent-based simulations (ABM). It is usual for the ABM models to have data distributions and scenarios that represent a large number of simulations. Simulation that one can parameterize and execute concurrently and for which HPC is a useful tool to calculate and execute. However, configuration and adaptation of simulation parameters and passing them to an HPC environment is extremely complex for users who are not familiar with this methodology, even if they use a queuing system in an HPC environment where the user should only access and execute a command.

In this proposal, we use Netlogo [1] as a kernel for ABM simulations. This is an environment for editing & visualizing ABM simulations using a Java runtime environment. Netlogo has extensive usage in social sciences, humanities or health sciences, and allows the concurrent executions of different scenarios through an internal module, called **Behavior Space**, but only can run a number of processes equivalent to the number of cores of the underlying architecture. In many cases the scale of variables, or the number of repetitions which are required to obtain statistically valid data, exceed the hundreds or thousands of combinations, and this feature is insufficient to obtain results in an acceptable time.

This case study describes a methodology used for the parametric execution of different scenarios with multiple replications on the HPC clusters based on '[Fire Propagation Model](#)' (standard ABM model included in Netlogo library [15]). In addition, users can adapt the proposed methodology to other simulation

kernels/models and the methodology can extend, with the appropriate connectors, to the HPC cloud services. The presented work organization is as follows: Section II shows different references of the ABM execution models in the HPC environments and in section III the proposed methodology and developed environment explained. Section IV gives details of the performed experiments and the performance measures obtained from the execution of the proposed model in Netlogo on the HPC cluster, also describes the most important conclusion from the results of these executions. Finally, sections V and VI present the conclusions/future work and references respectively.

II. STATE OF ART

Different tools and environments can be found in ABM execution models using different simulation methods and infrastructure kernels as viewed in [2,3]. If we consider selection criteria as environments, supporting parallel and/or distributed ABM simulation, we can list them as D-Mason [4], EcoLab [5], FLAME [6], MobiDyc [7], Pandora [8], and Repast HPC [9] and as concurrent execution Netlogo [1] but only for the Behavior Space.

D-Mason is a parallel extension of the MASON library [10] that allows writing and executing simulations of agent-based models. EcoLab was initially designed to support an abstract ecology model and allows agent partitioning over processors and fault tolerance support. FLAME (FLexible Agent-based Modeling Environment) is a code-generated tool that allows the user to define their agent-based model and automatically generates optimized C code for efficient parallel processing [11] and MobiDyc aims to develop agent-based models in fields of ecology and biology. Pandora is an ABMS tool from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center that have been used in various projects related to archeology and Repast HPC is an agent-based modeling and simulation environment that implements the main concepts of Repast Symphony with support for parallel-distributed environments. The object of this design is to obtain maximum scalability in supercomputers for large project simulations.

Unlike the previous ones, Netlogo was designed as an academic project with teaching/education objectives. However, its usability characteristics (including editing/simulation/visualization in the same environment), in addition to a friendly interface and a simple programming API, it has become a reference in different areas where the simulation adds a strategic value but its users are distant of technological environments. Netlogo uses the Java RTE and can run without difficulties on any computer/OS or in a browser with a Java plugin (applet mode). The main Netlogo limitation is that only supports multithreading in the Behavior Space tool, so its performance is limited to the number of cores/threads in the local infrastructure. Different initiatives

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have emerged, such as [12,16] that allow the parametric execution of Netlogo scenarios on an HPC cluster using script files that help the execution and distribution of work on the cluster nodes,

In recent years, new environments have emerged based on workflow formalisms such as OpenMOLE [13] and SCOOP [14]. OpenMOLE is a workflow engine for the exploration of simulation models that use high performance computing where they transparently delegate their concurrent executions to the remote execution environment. SCOOP is a distributed task environment that allows concurrent parallel programming in multiple environments.

Although these environments provide extended functionality and considerable performance in different languages/frameworks, none of them has turned out to have a simple interface for using HPC environment as an elastic environment for ABM model simulation. Except in a few exceptions, most of them require a series of technological knowledge to interact with the environment, to recode the model, to integrate it with the simulator/framework, to configure the environment or to generate the workflow that makes them unviable for a community of scientists, which only need the ABM simulation as an instrument.

III. METHODOLOGY

In order to provide an easy to use and user-friendly solution for non-technical users, we have created a workflow using different tools, collaborating in simulation of ABM on a HPC cluster. The execution of this workflow is unassisted and the initial user interaction is through an interface based on Web technology. On the local environment, the user configures his model, performs the local tests, sets up the Behavior Space and, through a service, schedule his model, and indicates where and how he wants to run.

In the developed environment's, the Frontend service analyzes the user-specified model. From this, generates all configuration files required for the proposed simulation scenarios, creates the initialization files for the high-performance cluster queue system and then sends them to Backend. There the system executes the experiment and when it finishes, user can see the result through the same web interface. Figure 1 shows the proposed architecture.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the environment

The tool for Frontend infrastructure is implemented in Python. Frontend interface uses a splitter module to obtain the data of the different simulation scenarios

configured by the user within the Behavior Space [15]. This module (based on [16]) performs the separation of the different ABM simulation scenarios by generating a configuration XML files for each of the combinations of the variables defined in the experiment set indicated by the user. These configuration files are a parametric simulation with a subset of the "data space" of this model (scenario). Each simulation with its data set will run on a HPC node concurrently with other simulations with a different data set, reducing the overall execution time of the user-defined data space. The implementation process in the proposed infrastructure consists of three stages:

1. Initialization and integration,
2. Deployment and
3. Execution.

In the first phase, the interface receives data files and user's model, and then the interface backend analyzes the experiments and after that, generates configuration and initialization of XML files in the HPC queuing system automation.

In the second phase, the deployment of the configuration and simulation data is made to cluster master node.

Finally, in the third phase, the execution starts and the backend waits for the results to forward them to the user.

In order to maintain the confidentiality of the data during the whole process, the interaction with the Frontend/Backend is through secure protocols (https in the case of Fronted and SSH+PKI in the case of the cluster). Figure 2 shows the steps that are performed in the proposed infrastructure and figure 3 is an example of the graphical user interface.

Fig. 2. Stages of the ABM simulation execution process.

Fig. 3. User interface.

As it can be seen in Figure 3, task 53 (job_id) is running (indicated by the red status icon) and task 54 has been deployed, but they have not sent to execution as indicated by the green arrow in the state. To start the process, the user simply must click on this arrow and this will start execution of the model on the cluster.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

To perform a proof of concept and analyze the performance of the entire environment we used an adaptation of the Fire.nlogo model (included in the Netlogo library [15]).

This model is simulated to show the propagation of a fire line in the forest. The probability that the fire can reach a target (the right edge of the simulation environment in this case) depends critically on the density of the trees. According to their authors, this is a typical model, representative of complex systems with a nonlinear threshold. Its function is very simple: the fire begins at the forest in the left border of simulation environment, and overspreads to the neighboring trees in four main possible directions (north, east, south and west). In this version of the model, the wind speed is considered zero so the fire must have trees along its path to move forward in this direction. If there are no trees in one direction, the fire stop their propagation in this path.

Fig. 4. Interactive graphical visualization interface of the Fire.nlogo simulation on Netlogo.

Figure 4 is the Netlogo graphical interface of the simulation with the parameter density of the forest equal to 60%.

The first experiment was the execution on 8 cores of the simulation for a fixed size of the terrain and 2 repetitions of each simulation considering different values of density. Figure 4 shows two repetitions of simulation time and number of burned trees (cells) for the same density. As can be observed, the stochastic nature of the process implies that the patterns of burned cells are different for every simulation time and the objective function has also a different simulation time. This characteristic of these models increase the need for number of replication to have statistically feasible data and justify the necessity of the use of HPC.

Fig. 4. Comparison of two executions experiments for the same density values.

Figure 5 shows the scalability of a fixed density value, while distributing the replicates to the different cores in the HPC cluster. As can be observed, the speedup results are very satisfying, although by starting from 32 cores, the values of speedup begin to move away from the linear value. The justification for it is that all cores share the disk and, although there are no communications between the executions because they are parametric simulations, the input/output is in the same NFS disk and this does as containment system for a high number of processes. However, it can be observed that the performance of the HPC architecture is fine and the efficiency values remain above 87%.

Fig. 5. Speedup and efficiency from 8 to 64 cores.

To verify the penalization imposed by NFS input/output shared space (Java Virtual Machine code, the simulator kernel, the model and data), an experiment executed on 32 and 64 cores has been made. Figure 6 shows a box diagram with the minimum and maximum values, the median and Q1-Q3 values obtained from the execution time for the different repetitions of the same experiment. As can be observed from the figure, the dispersion values on 32 cores are very small (see minimal and maximum values) and the distribution is symmetrical. On 64 cores, the dispersion of values is much greater and the distribution is not symmetrical (observe the values of Q1 and Q3 on 64 cores).

Since the values of speedup and efficiency are better for 32 cores, we can conclude that the recommended configurations for this case is this architecture, since the best values are obtained under the conditions that imposes Netlogo/Java and access to shared resources.

Fig. 6. Mean, median, min/max, Q1/Q3 values for execution time on 32 and 64 cores.

In addition to the limitations imposed by shared disk I/O, one of the most important considerations of Netlogo+Java is the amount of memory required for large-size models. This consideration may be a limitation in local environments. In order to consider this effect, an experiment has been designed to expose the model memory requirements by varying the size of the space to be simulated in x2, x4, x6 factors. For this case, we have carried out simulations on 32 processors on world sizes from 100x100 to 600x600. Figure 7 shows the performance and efficiency factors for this experiment. As can be observed in x6 models performance (and efficiency), fall significantly.

Although this is not an issue imposed by the HPC architecture, it is necessary consider this situation to orient to researcher to introduce changes in the model. The researcher should convert the model (or redesign) to avoid the large model data utilization which will result in a performance reductions. The memory problems for large models is a common issue in the Netlogo community and basically are defined by the amount of memory required to represent the agent's elements and by the constraints imposed by the Java runtime environment.

Fig. 7. Speedup and efficiency over 32 cores for different sizes of simulated space (up to x6).

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The agent-based simulation is a technique widely used in areas not close to High Performance Computing (HPC) and which require a large amount of resources for the parametric simulation of large scenarios and with a large number of interrelationships between individuals. In addition, in these areas of knowledge such as social

sciences, humanities or health science, tools such as Netlogo provide a high value since it allows design and simulate ABM models in a simple way and obtain results to support the different lines of research.

However, when the number of individuals/interrelations between them is increased, or experimental spaces are designed that include a large number of variables, local resources are insufficient or represents large execution times. In this sense, the HPC is an excellent option, but it is necessary to adapt the environment for people not near to this area/tools.

In the present work, a methodology and an environment have been described that allow in a simple and unattended form to send the experimentation to an HPC cluster using a service and collecting the results of the execution. That is, the researcher has a local environment where the experiments are designed (using Behavior Space Environment of Netlogo as usual) and them using a web interface, uploads his model/experiment and sends it to simulate without knowing how and where it is executed.

As can be seen from the experiments carried out, the HPC infrastructure adds value to this experimentation and does not pose a problem for the researcher who only wants to run his experiments in the shortest possible time and without worrying about the underlying environment.

The speedup and efficiency values obtained for the model are satisfying although in some cases the input/output shared between the cores (for the Java and Netlogo environment) impose some restrictions that make the values not so acceptable for a high number of cores. In addition, other limitations related to the memory required for the execution of Netlogo (and the Java environment), that are common in the community, have been detected and require that the model be redesigned to solve them.

Future work goals are as follows:

- To perform scalability and performance tests with different models and range of experiments.
- To integrate it with a production system to see the behavior, scalability and efficiency with different users/models/experiments.
- To improve the presentation of results to the user (currently the experimentation output is showed in a file form).
- To develop the necessary connectors to extend the functionality of the HPC environment over a private/public cloud environment.

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VI. REFERENCIAS

- [1] Wilensky, U. "NetLogo". 1999. Center for Connected Learning and Computer-Based Modeling, Northwestern Institute on Complex Systems, Evanston. <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>
- [2] Nikolai, C., G. Madey. 2009. "Tools of the Trade: A Survey of Various Agent Based Modeling Platforms". Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation 12(2).
- [3] Allan, R. 2010. "Survey of Agent Based Modelling and Simulation Tools". STFC Daresbury Laboratory, Daresbury, Warrington. DL-TR-2010-007. ISSN 1362-0207. <http://purl.org/net/epubs/work/50398>

- [4] Cordasco, G., R. Chiara, A. Mancuso, D. Mazzeo, V. Scarano, C. Spagnuolo. 2013. "Bringing Together Efficiency and Effectiveness in Distributed Simulations: The Experience with D-Mason". *Simulation* 89(10):1236 - 1253.
- [5] Standish, R., R. Leow. 2003. "Ecolab: Agent Based Modeling for C++ Programmers". CoRR. 2004. <https://arxiv.org/abs/cs/0401026>.
- [6] Coakley, S., M. Gheorghe, M. Holcombe, S. Chin, D. Worth, C. Greenough. 2012. "Exploitation of High Performance Computing in the FLAME Agent-Based Simulation Framework". In 2012 IEEE 14th International Conference on High Performance Computing and Communication 538-545.
- [7] Ginot, V., C. Page, S. Souissi, S. 2002. "A Multi-agents Architecture to Enhance End-user Individual-Based Modelling". *Ecological Modelling* 157(1):23-41.
- [8] Rubio-Campillo, X. 2014. "Pandora: A Versatile Agent-Based Modelling Platform for Social Simulation". In Proceedings of SIMUL, the Sixth International Conference on Advances in System Simulation, 29-34.
- [9] North, M.J., N.T. Collier, and J.R. Vos. 2006. "Experiences Creating Three Implementations of the Repast Agent Modeling Toolkit". *ACM Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation* 16 (1):1-25.
- [10] Luke, S., C. Cioffi-Revilla, L. Panait, K. Sullivan, G. Balan. 2005. "Mason: A Multiagent Simulation Environment". *Simulation* 81 (7):517-527.
- [11] Holcombe, M., S. Coakley, R. Smallwood. 2006. "A General Framework for Agent-based Modelling of Complex Systems. In Proceedings of the European Conference on Complex Systems
- [12] Netlogo-cluster. 2015. <https://github.com/jurnix/netlogo-cluster>.
- [13] Reuillon, R., M. Leclaire, S. Rey-Coyrehourcq. 2013. "OpenMOLE, a Workflow Engine Specifically Tailored for the Distributed Exploration of Simulation Models". *Future Generation Computer Systems* 29(8):1981-1990.
- [14] Hold-Geoffroy, Y., O. Gagnon, and M. Parizeau. 2014. "Once You SCOOP, No Need to Fork". Annual Conference on Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment, ACM, Article No. 60:1-8.
- [15] Walker, E., C. Guiang. 2007. "Challenges in Executing Large Parameter Sweep Studies Across Widely Distributed Computing Environments". In Proceedings of the 5th IEEE workshop on Challenges of large applications in distributed environments 11-18
- [16] Lukas Ahrenberg. 2013. License: GNU GLP 3. https://github.com/ahrenberg/split_nlogo_experiment.
- [17] Wilensky, U., W. Rand. 2007. "Making Models Match: Replicating an Agent-based Model". *JASSS* 10(4).